

METHODS OF APPLYING INTERACTIVE METHODS TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.

Rustamova Mavluda Yunus qizi.

Maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'limda xorijiy til yo'nalishi , 1-kurs 542-22 guruh talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7549693>

Abstract: In the 2022 Proclamation of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M.Mirziyoyev , he proposed and recommended that great attention should be paid to preschool education. Today, preschool education system is receiving more attention than other areas. The reason for this is that pre-school educational institutions and kindergartens play an incomparable role in the development of mature staff and in determining the interests and abilities of children. This article describes the systematic work in this field, the support of interactive technologies and methods in preschool children, as well as the facts and analyzes of foreign experience.

Key words: interactive, technology, methods, preschool education, child psychology, etc.

Children, like adults, are always engaged in certain activities. While adults are busy with the production of socially useful things that are needed for other people, the main goal of children's activities is based on learning. Preschool children's activities can include games, drawing, making something out of plasticine or clay, applique, construction, and so on. Children usually engage in certain activities with the instructions and suggestions of their parents. Only in some cases, the children themselves perform this or that activity independently. In both cases, children's activities will have a certain result. Activity products are studied based on the results of children's activities. Often, the product of children's activities is studied by looking at their drawings, objects made of clay or plasticine. According to the psychology of children, it is important to send them to a pre-school educational institution and to form their future field according to their current abilities. Today, interactive technology and methods are introduced into the educational system in this field.

There is no doubt that interactive learning is an interesting, creative, promising direction of pedagogy. It helps to realize all the possibilities of preschool children, taking into account their psychological capabilities. The use of interactive technologies allows to enrich the knowledge and presentation of children in the world around the world, encourages children to actively interact in the system of social relations about relationships with peers and adults. Several learning models differ in the field of pedagogy:

Passive - the child works as an "object" of training (listening and watching) an active child works as a "subject" of training (independent work, creative tasks)

Interactive - interaction between the child and the teacher. It should also be noted that the main tasks of such training and education are: development of children's initiative and mutual independence; Forming the ability to learn and independently produce information; Integration with children; Communication between children and adults; Active involvement of the child in society. Today, several interactive technological activities are used in preschool educational institutions in our country. For instance: "Working in small groups (Troika)" the application of this work technology allows working on the basis of all children. Children should evaluate their independent work, not only their own but also their friend's work, communicate and help each other learns. Chain" The basis of this technology is the participant's search for a coherent solution to one task. The existence of a common goal and the atmosphere of mutual support provide opportunities to embrace each other, solve tasks, and form the ability of children to work in a team. "Tree of knowledge" develops communication skills in children, forms the ability to negotiate and feel responsibility in solving tasks. Interactive training is one of the types of active learning method. Interactive learning interaction is not only between the teacher and preschool children, but all the many students work together (or work in groups). Interactive learning methods are always interaction, collaboration, search, communication, play between people or human and information environment. Using active and interactive learning methods in lessons, the teacher increases the amount of material read by students up to 90 percent. It is mainly used for interactive technologies and educational methods in preschool educational institutions. For a preschool teacher, the game is the main activity, and through it you can teach everything necessary at the age of the child. There are various games to attract children's attention to the lesson. For example: Play-Way method. Children love to play and laugh, and this preschool uses play as a learning method. They learn structured activities through play. Thus, it can be combined with other methods, as well as in classrooms. Because the focus is on fun and play, children often enjoy the preschool style of education. Bank street method. The goal of this method is to encourage children to be lifelong learners. Instead of just memorizing facts, children are given other ways to learn, such as puzzles, field trips, and blocks. It is non-competitive in the classroom, encouraging children to learn at their own pace and through interactions with their peers. The game is one of the main elements that we use for learning. Immersion in the language. Some people think that learning languages is easier when you are young. Learning a second language

can advance a child's career or preserve your family's cultural background and connections. Immigrant preschools exist to help with this goal. They can help introduce children to languages they don't speak at home or reinforce parents' efforts to teach them another language. You can choose to be partially or fully immersed. Partly, about half of the time of preschool age is spent on language learning. Some preschools emphasize helping children develop STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math) skills. Rather than requiring students to simply memorize facts, STEM-based programs seek to create independent thinkers. The student learns about solving problems, asking questions, conducting experiments, and making observations. While this is obviously not nearly as engaging as STEM work done in elementary and middle schools, the theory is that it gives kids a good start. But there is another side of the issue. Many parents do not understand the benefits of preschool education. It is important for teachers to demonstrate the value of the preschool program and explain how everything they do in the classroom is preparing their child for kindergarten and beyond. Preschool education is an important time in a child's life not only because it is a great opportunity to communicate in life, but also because it creates the foundation for becoming a well-rounded student and person throughout his life. Should include language, science and mathematics at the experience level of three- and four-year-old children. No matter what type or style of preschool you choose, your child should feel comfortable with it because they will be spending a lot of time with their caregivers. You don't want them to feel pressured or restricted in preschool, which can lead them to believe that they don't like school at all, which can cause problems for the rest of their academic career. Having a positive attitude toward learning because they find it fun is key to unlocking their overall happiness and long-term success. No matter which method you choose, they will learn something and every lesson is important to their development. Because interactive technologies allow to successfully solve problems: free communication with adults and children; development of all components of children's oral speech; to contribute to the practical skills of students of speech standards. In conclusion, there are other different methods taught by different institutes of the world. Despite being different in terms of approach, it is not always possible to separate these methods into specific teaching methods. Many times, different approaches may be appropriate to some degree, as well as depending on the needs of different children. However, what these different methods reflect is the effort made by the institution to meet the child's needs. These methods also reflect the need for the child to have active contact with the preschool.

References:

- 1.M. Vahidov. Child psychology. Tashkent. "Teacher" - 1882
- 2.Yagyaeva, E. B. SOME METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHERS OF ENGLISH-2012
- 3.Bakhtiyarovna, Y. E. Portfolio as an assessment tool for individualized instruction - 2019
- 4.Bakhtiyarovna, Y. E. The main problems encountered in a second / foreign language acquisition in technical higher educational institutions-2019